

Experiments with Precipitated and Colloidal Manganese Dioxide.

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It has been suggested (Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 649, 997 and earlier papers) that on coagulation the electric charge of the coagulated particles is completely neutralised and that this changes their adsorbing properties (*ibid*, 1924, 28, 465. See also Weiser, *ibid*, 1920, 24, 30, 630). An attempt has also been made (Dhar, *loc. cit.*) to correlate (1) the influence of the dilution of a sol on the coagulating concentration of electrolytes, (2) ionic antagonism and (3) acclimatization through the adsorption of similarly charged ions by the colloidal particle and a 'normal' and an 'abnormal' dilution rule have been proposed as follows: 'Normally,' the greater the dilution of a sol, the less would be the amount of electrolyte necessary to coagulate it, provided that the relative adsorption of similarly charged ions by the sol does not increase on dilution. A higher coagulating concentration would be 'abnormal' and is to be attributed to the adsorption of similarly charged ions. These conceptions have been the subject of some criticism. (See Weiser, *loc. cit.*; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 962; Dhar's reply, *ibid*, 1926, 30, 628; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 17).

Recent cataphoretic measurements (Mukherjee and co-workers, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 697, 785; *Nature*, 1928, 122, 608; Kruyt and Willigen, *Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 44, 22) establish, contrary to the assumptions referred to above, that coagulation takes place even when the colloidal particles carry considerable electrical charges and that it is not possible to speak of a critical potential (*Cf. Powis*).

Dhar and his co-workers (*loc. cit.*) have worked with both positive and negative manganese dioxide sols. In this paper the parallelism between 'abnormal' behaviour, adsorption of ions and ionic antagonism has been examined.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The 'negatively charged sols' were prepared according to Chakravarti and Dhar (*loc. cit.*). To a standard solution of potassium permanganate, hydrogen peroxide solution (Merck's 10 per cent. by vol.) was added at room temperature in small quantities with stirring until a test portion on coagulation with BaCl_2 left a colourless or slightly coloured upper layer.

The sol became unstable on dialysis in parchment paper bags, probably due to chemical reaction. The undialysed sols were stable for months and were used for experiments. The sol was treated with excess of standard oxalic acid (containing sulphuric acid), warmed to 60° and titrated against standard potassium permanganate solution. A and B contain respectively 0.443 g. and 0.610 g. of MnO_2 per litre. The total manganese in sol A determined by the phosphate method and calculated as MnO_2 was 0.527 g. per litre. The particles carried a negative charge as measured by the method of moving boundaries.

The positively charged sols were prepared according to Ghosh and Dhar (*loc. cit.*). A standard solution of ferric chloride is mixed with a solution of potassium permanganate. Hydrogen peroxide is then added in small quantities at a time and stirred till there is hardly any excess of permanganate. The sol is then dialysed for about 10 days until free from iron and chlorine. These sols are very stable even after dialysis.

Composition.—The dioxide (I), the total manganese expressed as dioxide (II) and iron as ferric oxide (III) in grams per litre of sol were for these sols as follows :

TABLE I.

	I	II	III
A ⁺	0.00	0.05	4.251
B ⁺	0.10	0.10	2.024
C ⁺	0.29	1.92	2.724

The particles carried a positive charge.

Manganese dioxide Precipitates, A and B, were prepared respectively according to Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 128, 2605) and to Sarkar and Dhar (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1922, 121, 135), washed free from

electrolytes and air-dried. 'A' contained 47.10 per cent. MnO_2 and 51.46 per cent. total manganese expressed as MnO_2 . The particles were found to be negatively charged. 'B' (dried in a steam oven) contained 41.12 per cent. MnO_2 and 58.34 per cent. total manganese calculated as MnO_2 . Endosmotic as also cataphoretic experiments with the sol formed by shaking the precipitates showed that the particles were negatively charged.

Equicoagulating concentrations were measured according to the procedure used before (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 794). Equicoagulating concentrations given below produced the same stage of coalescence in three minutes. For coagulation by a single electrolyte, a definite volume (5 c. c.) of the sol was taken in one tube and varying quantities of the electrolyte were taken in another tube together with sufficient amount of water to make the volume in the latter tube equal to 5 c. c. For dilutions 2.5 c. c. and 1.25 c. c. respectively of the sol were made up to 5 c. c. with water and electrolyte added as before.

For coagulation by a mixture of two electrolytes 5 c. c. of the sol were taken in one tube and in another an amount (insufficient for coagulation) of one electrolyte with varying amounts of the second and enough water to make the volume of the mixture (in the second tube) equal to 5 c. c.

Adsorption Experiments.

Precipitate.—A known weight of the precipitate was treated with 50 c.c. of the electrolyte in Jena glass bottles and after vigorous shaking the contents were left in contact for 24 hours. The supernatant liquid was then pipetted off and analysed for the concentration of the various ions. In some cases the p_{H} value of the liquid was determined and compared to that of the salt solutions used. The experiments were repeated with half and one-fourth amounts of the precipitate.

Sols.—20 C.c. were treated with 30 c. c. of the electrolyte. After shaking and leaving overnight the supernatant liquid was analysed. The experiments were repeated by taking 10 c. c. of the sol and adding 10 c. c. of water and 30 c. c. of the electrolyte.

*Results and Discussion.**Adsorption Experiments.*

TABLE II.

Conc. of sol.	Gram equivalent of electrolyte present per litre.	Amount adsorbed in g. equivalents of		Ratio of adsorption Anion/Cation.
		Cation	Anion.	
20 C. c. sol	0.061N-BaCl ₂	0.000582	0.000485	0.833
10 C. c. sol + 10 c. c. water	0.061 N-BaCl ₂	0.000544	0.000454	0.8345
20 C. c. sol	0.1176 N-CuCl ₂	0.0015	0.00132	0.88
10 C. c. sol + 10 c. c. water	0.1176 N-CuCl ₂	0.00136	0.00127	0.93

TABLE III.

Coagulating Concentrations.

Sol A ⁻ .	KCl.	BaCl ₂ .	AlCl ₃ .	AlCl ₃ .
1 : 1	0.051 N	0.00071 N	0.0021 N*	0.0012 N (0.1050N)**
1 : 3	0.060 N	0.00049 N	0.0011 N*	(0.1245 N)**
1 : 7	0.120 N	0.00021 N	0.00091 N*	(0.2394 N)**

TABLE IV.

Ionic Antagonism.

Sol B ⁻ .	% of KCl.	% of NaCl.	% of BaCl ₂ .	% of AlCl ₃ .
0	100 (0.292 N)†	—	100 (0.0092 N)	100 (0.018N)
4.6	—	—	89.1	—
9.3	—	89.5	—	87.7
18.6	—	—	58.7	—
23.2	—	75.4	—	73.1
46.5	—	50.9	28.3	55.2
100	100 (0.368N)†	0	0	0

* Another sample C⁻ for which the coagulating concentration of KCl was 0.066N.

** The second coagulating concentration presumably after reversal.

† NaCl has a greater coagulating power than KCl contrary to the observation of Ghosh and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 189), who however used a sol dialysed free from alkali. With another sol (undialysed), the following coagulating concentrations were observed : KCl, 0.0668N ; NaCl, 0.084N.

TABLE V.
Ionic Antagonism.

Sol A⁻.

% of KCl.	% of BaCl ₂ .	% of K ₂ SO ₄ .	% of K ₃ PO ₄ .	% of K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ .
0	100 (.00071 N)	100 (.0432 N)	100 (.0954 N)	100 (.055 N)
9.1	66.2	—	—	—
18.2	53.5	75	85.3	56.7
36.4	28.2	54.2	66.7	23.3
54.5	—	29.2	42.1	—
100 (.0509 N)	0	0	0	0

Aluminium has a weaker coagulating power than barium. Ghosh and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) observed the same thing. On dilution the sol behaves like arsenious sulphide, being stabilised against potassium ions and sensitised against barium and aluminium (first coagulation), contrary to Dhar and Ghosh, who observed uniform sensitisation on dilution. Evidently the present sol, though prepared in the same manner, indicates an 'abnormal' behaviour. It should therefore show 'ionic antagonism' as both are stated by Dhar to be correlated through a common cause, namely, a strong preferential adsorption of similarly charged ions. Tables IV and V signify however that the expected ionic antagonism is completely absent. Ghosh and Dhar also did not observe any ionic antagonism with their sol nor observe a higher coagulating concentration of potassium chloride. The so-called normal or abnormal behaviour thus depends on the particular preparation even if the same method be adopted.

Table II (as also the results of Dhar and co-workers) shows that cations are adsorbed more strongly than anions. We think however that on dilution, the ratio of their adsorption (probably) remains constant within the limits of error. Dhar ascribes the sensitisation to a relatively greater adsorption of the oppositely charged ion as a result of the dilution and stabilisation to that of the similarly charged ion. It is not obvious why dilution as such must have this effect. Assuming an equilibrium and that the properties of the particles do not change on dilution (see later), a greater adsorption will be observed only when the amounts adsorbed are great compared to the

total amount present, so that the equilibrium concentration increases. But this need not necessarily change either the amount adsorbed, if the concentration is high, or the ratio of their adsorptions in the manner assumed by Dhar.

The coagulation with aluminium (Table II) shows in the first zone of precipitation a 'normal' and in the second an 'abnormal' behaviour, which is to be interpreted as showing that the ratio of its adsorption to that of chlorine increases throughout the range of concentrations. As the particles are negatively charged in the first zone and positively in the second, we have sensitisation in the one case and stabilisation in the other. The ratio of adsorption should however tend to a constant value, as the concentration increases; but, the rapid increase in the coagulating concentration, in the second zone, points to the contrary. Further different types of curves are met with in adsorption phenomena indicating that the ratio of adsorption may show a very complicated behaviour on dilution.

There are other more serious objections against the simple explanation of Dhar. It ignores the actual effects of dilution. Recent work (Mukherjee and co-workers, *loc. cit.*, also results communicated for publication) shows that, though on dilution the sol becomes sensitised, the cataphoretic speeds of particles of ferric hydroxide sols show a *decrease or an increase*, depending on the preparation and the degree of dilution. A detailed consideration of the large number of factors concerned thus appears to be required. Moreover, estimation of amounts of ions adsorbed cannot give a definite idea as to their effect on the stability. Thus an oppositely charged ion may be associated with a colloidal particle either in a 'free' (mobile) or in a 'fixed' (on the solid side of the interface) state. When such an ion passes from the 'free' to the 'fixed' state or *vice versa*, chemical analysis cannot possibly indicate the difference, though it will have an obvious effect on the stability. Discussions as to the effect of relative changes in adsorption of the cation and anion, deduced from chemical analysis, are therefore futile and misleading. Similarly the distinction between adsorption by charged and neutral particles, that is supposed to be different and to occur as independent processes before and after coagulation, has no justification in fact, as coagulation seldom takes place at the isoelectric point.

The relative adsorptions of copper and chlorine ions also go against the above rule, as Dhar and Ghosh observed a normal behaviour with negative sols. The ratio anion to cation should decrease

instead of the slight increase observed in Table II. Lastly on account of the small quantities adsorbed, it is not desirable to place too much stress on the values of these ratios.

TABLE VI.

Adsorption.

Sol C ⁺ .				
Conc. of sol.	G. equivalent of electrolyte present per litre.	Amount absorbed in g. equivalent of Cation Anion.		Ratio of adsorption Cation/Anion.
20 C.c. of sol	0.592 N-CuCl ₂	·00053	·000†	—
10 C.c. of sol + 10 c.c. of water	0.592 N-CuCl ₂	·0011	·000†	—
20 C.c. of sol	0.54 N-BaCl ₂	·00084	·00026	1.80
10 C.c. of sol + 10 c.c. of water	0.54 N-BaCl ₂	·00028	·00020	1.40

TABLE VII.

Sol A⁺.

Coagulating Concentrations in Normality

Conc. of sol.	KCl.	KNO ₃ *.	K ₂ SO ₄ .	K ₂ C ₂ O ₄ .	K ₃ PO ₄ .	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ .
1 : 1	·0092	·0952	·000456	·000452	·000595	·000061
1 : 3	·0111	·1130	·000288	·000288	·000268	·000041
1 : 7	·0134	·1250	·000205	·000205	·000189	·000053

TABLE VIII.

Ionic Antagonism.

Sol C ⁺ .				
% of KCl.	% of KNO ₃ .	% of K ₂ SO ₄ .	% of K ₃ PO ₄ .	% of K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ .
0	100 (·0952 N)	100 (·00123 N)	100 (·00123 N)	100 (·00024 N)
5.55	98.75	—	71.8	73.8
8.33	—	74.1	—	—
19.44	68.75	55.55	38.5	52.3
41.65	50.00	33.33	20.55	28.6
100 (·0666 N)	0	0	0	0

* The coagulating concentrations of KNO₃ are for another sample. For this sample the coagulating concentration of KCl was 0.066 N.

† Adsorption within experimental error.

TABLE IX.

Ionic Antagonism.

Sol B ⁺ . % of KCl.	% of K ₂ SO ₄ .	% of NaCl.	% of MgCl ₂ .
0	100 (.00046 N)	100 (.0184 N)	100 (.0177 N)
5	95	1.7	103
10	80	—	—
20	70	80.5	85.3
40	45	55.8	—
50	—	—	56
60	—	41	—
100 (.0185 N)	0	0	0

TABLE X.

Ionic Antagonism.

Sol B ⁺ . % of K ₂ SO ₄ .	% of Na ₂ SO ₄ .	% of MgSO ₄ .
0	100 (.0005 N)	100 (.00051 N)
10	90	92.8
30	70	70
50	50	54
100 (.00045 N)	0	0

Sol A⁺ obeys Schultze-Hardy law (Table VII) and the coagulating concentrations are in the order.—NO₃>Cl>SO₄. C₂O₄. PO₄>Fe(CN)₆. On dilution it behaves like the negative sol (of course against anions). Here also the observations of Dhar and his co-workers with the chloride and the nitrate (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 192) are contrary to ours, as they observed a normal behaviour; ionic antagonism is again absent with these two electrolytes though expected.

With barium chloride, the ratio of the adsorption of cation to anion does not change on dilution; the amounts after adsorption were respectively barium, 1.8314 and 1.8355 and chlorine .9498 and .9512. The difference in the ratio is to be ascribed to the manner of estimating the adsorption by the very small differences in the concentrations. In the case of cupric chloride, copper appears to be

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adsorbed but not chlorine ion. The observations in the previous section apply equally.

TABLE XI.

Adsorption Experiments.

Precipitate A.				
Amount in g.	G. equivalents of electrolyte per litre.	Amount adsorbed in g. equivalents of :		Ratio of adsorption Cation/Anion.
		Cation.	Anion.	
2.4806	.1014 BaCl ₂	.00127	.00103	1.23
4.1773	.1014 BaCl ₂	.00127	.00104	1.22
2.0059	.153 CuCl ₂	.000044	.00055	.08
4.5942	.153 CuCl ₂	.00047	.00555	.085

We again find that the ratio remains practically constant. Dhar and his co-workers, however, found that the ratio, cation to anion, increases as the quantity of the adsorbent decreases.

TABLE XII.

Adsorption Experiments.

Precipitate B.

Amount of ppt. taken in g.	G. equivalent of electrolyte per litre.	Amount adsorbed in g. equivalents of :		Ratio of adsorption Cation/Anion.
		Cation.	Anion.	
.5788	.1014 BaCl ₂	.0012	.00064	1.875
1.0112	.1014 BaCl ₂	.0014	.00093	1.505
.5354	.196 CuCl ₂	.0024	.00213	1.126
.9908	.196 CuCl ₂	.00285	.00219	1.301
1.8691	.196 CuCl ₂	.0036	.00213	1.690

The copper is adsorbed more than chlorine (Table XII) but the ratio decreases with a diminution in the amount and contrary to the observations of Dhar and his co-workers of an increase, which is in support of their hypothesis. Precipitates A and B are negatively charged. Dhar does not distinguish between adsorption by the 'positive' sol (containing iron) and by the 'negative' precipitates, as they account for the stabilisation of the former against copper chloride on the basis of the adsorption of the latter. This is also in contrast with the distinction between neutral and charged particles. It appears from the data given below that the relative adsorption in the case of the positive sol depends on the sample (probably on the iron content):

TABLE XIII_a

Positive Sol:		Electrolyte — CuCl ₂ .	
Our Observation : Vol. sol A (c. c.).	Conc. (normal).	Iron content g. of Fe ₂ O ₃ per litre of sol.	Ratio of adsorption. Cation/Anion.
20	.592	2.724	$\frac{.00653^*}{0}$
10	"	"	$\frac{.0011^*}{0}$

(Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 1029, 1930).

20	.01	Not given	10.7
10	"	"	9.1

Dhar and Sarkar (*loc. cit.*) have pointed out the formation of manganates by the interaction of neutral electrolytes and potassium permanganates. This reaction and the stability of the manganates will depend on the hydrogen-ion concentration among other things. In the positively charged sol we have used, the amount of iron is considerable in comparison with the manganese content. The question arises whether we are to consider it as a sol of manganese dioxide or ferric manganate or a complex solid containing different solid phases, whose constitution can only be determined by separate

* The ratio of adsorption of cation to anion in this case bears no significance.

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investigations. The positive sol adsorbs scarcely any chlorine but copper relatively strongly. The p^{∞} of the supernatant liquid after coagulation of the positive sol is about 6.1 for barium chloride. The liberation of the chlorine at higher concentration is also not ruled out. It may not thus be profitable to discuss the results on the basis, that we are dealing with the same chemical substance in both sols (positive and negative—see also difference in composition of the precipitate) and that chemical reactions, changing the composition of the colloid (either *en masse* or of several layers of molecules on the surface) are ruled out.

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